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Using Deep Learning to Model the Groundwater Tracer Radon in Coastal Waters

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Key Points:

- We show how deep learning can predict coastal seawater radon, a popular groundwater discharge tracer
- One model, intended for short-term forecasts and gap filling, correctly predicted radon ($r^2 > 0.80$) at hydrologically diverse study sites
- A second model accurately predicts radon ($r^2 > 0.76$) using only water depth, temperature, salinity, air temperature, and wind speed

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

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Abstract Submarine groundwater discharge (SGD) is an important driver of coastal biogeochemical budgets worldwide. Radon (^{222}Rn) has been widely used as a natural geochemical tracer to quantify SGD, but field measurements are time consuming and costly. Here, we use deep learning to predict coastal seawater radon in SGD-impacted regions. We hypothesize that deep learning could resolve radon trends and enable preliminary insights with limited field observations of groundwater tracers. Two deep learning models were trained on global coastal seawater radon observations ($n = 39,238$) with widely available inputs (e.g., salinity, temperature, water depth). The first model used a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN-RNN) framework for site-specific gap filling and producing short-term future predictions. A second model applied a fully connected neural network (FCNN) framework to predict radon across geographically and hydrologically diverse settings. Both models can predict observed radon concentrations with $r^2 > 0.76$. Specifically, the FCNN model offers a compelling development because synthetic radon tracer data sets can be obtained using only basic water quality and meteorological parameters. This opens opportunities to attain radon data from regions with large data gaps, such as the Global South and other remote locations, allowing for insights that can be used to predict SGD and plan field experiments. Overall, we demonstrate how field-based measurements combined with big-data approaches such as deep learning can be utilized to assess radon and potentially SGD beyond local scales.

1. Introduction

Submarine groundwater discharge (SGD) significantly impacts local-scale coastal water and chemical budgets (e.g., Luijendijk et al., 2020; Santos et al., 2021; Taniguchi et al., 2019). Total SGD, which is comprised of both fresh (terrestrial) and saline (recirculated seawater) components, may be as high as 3 to 4 times that of river discharge, particularly in volcanic island settings (Kwon et al., 2014). SGD carries nutrient, metal, carbon, and micropollutant loads to the ocean that rival or exceed those from rivers (e.g., Cho et al., 2018; Moore, 2010; Rahman et al., 2019). Despite its importance, SGD research is mostly absent from extensive areas of the globe, including the Global South, in part because of the required specialization in detection of geochemical radiotracers such as radon and radium, as well as the financial burden, accessibility of sites, and overall technical feasibility of conducting these measurements.

Continuous radon measurements in time represent an effective tool for monitoring SGD dynamics at tidal, seasonal, and interannual scales (Dulai et al., 2016; McKenzie et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2009). Currently, radon is the only SGD tracer that has been measured using automated techniques to produce large temporal data sets. While radon-based SGD estimates have well-defined shortcomings and uncertainties (e.g., Adyasari et al., 2023; Taniguchi et al., 2019), the applicability of radon has been demonstrated in a wide variety of coastal settings. Longer-term SGD measurements are vital for protecting water resources and coastal water quality under climate change (e.g., sea level rise, drought, increasing storm event frequency, and severity), land use changes, and coastal aquifer overpumping. Most available radon data sets span <1 week in duration because it is difficult to maintain instrumentation in remote areas for longer-term deployments. Since radon is currently the only groundwater tracer that can be measured continuously, it is necessary to develop opportunities for optimizing its usage.

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A. Deep Learning Workflow

B. CNN-RNN Architecture

C. FCNN Architecture

Figure 1. Schematic of deep learning workflow and architecture. (a) Typical deep learning process consisting of data wrangling and preprocessing, model learning, and evaluation and final model output phases (e.g., Sarker, 2021). Processed data are split into training, validation, and test sets to train and assess model performance. (b) Example convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture. Data are input into the model consisting of a kernel of a predefined width where weights (e.g., w_1 , w_2) are learned through model training (e.g., Sarker, 2021). CNN models consist of a layer where convolution is performed following a pooling layer (the basic concept of average pooling is shown in the figure). Typically, this is followed by fully connected layers before resolving the final model output. (c) Example of a fully connected neural network (FCNN) model architecture where the input data (each input circle represents one variable) are trained, validated, and tested through the model consisting of hidden layers and a variable number of nodes, resulting in one or more output variables. During the training phase, the model learns the best weight to assign to each connection (e.g., Sarker, 2021).

A sufficiently large quantity of high-quality radon data has been produced to allow for use of big-data methods, such as statistics and machine learning. The use of deep learning (a class of machine learning algorithms) is rapidly increasing in hydrological sciences and outperforms other traditional methods when analyzing large data sets and making subsequent predictions (LeCun et al., 2015; Marçais & de Dreuzy, 2017). Deep learning is essentially a neural network model with multiple, “deep” layers consisting of input, intermediate (hidden), and output layers and capable of approximating any complex operations (LeCun et al., 2015; Figure 1). Deep learning identifies both linear and nonlinear relationships learned from the environmental big-data in a “black-box”

Figure 2. Locations of coastal radon time series data obtained for this study. Mean radon in water concentrations (Bq/m^3) for each study site are indicated by the color-coded scale.

fashion. In hydrology, deep learning can be implemented to accommodate abstract parameters and extract underlying relationships while minimizing the requirement for fully resolving underlying physical drivers as required by most hydrological models (Marçais & de Dreuzay, 2017).

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), Recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and fully connected neural networks (FCNNs) are three types of deep learning frameworks frequently applied in hydrology (Figure 1). CNNs work best with time series, image, and video data with hierarchical space-time patterns/correlations while RNNs are suitable for time series modeling and prediction by learning temporal dependency. FCNN's has a wide array of applications under no additional assumption. Deep learning has been used to model groundwater levels, stream flow, precipitation, recharge, and aquifer contamination (e.g., Forghani et al., 2021; Hadzima-Nyarko et al., 2014; Hsu et al., 2002; Hu et al., 2019; Kadeethum et al., 2021). However, many coastal processes, including SGD, have not yet been modeled using big-data approaches.

Here, we use deep learning to model radon in coastal waters as a basis to understand SGD dynamics and potentially obtain insight in areas lacking any data and filling gaps in areas with limited data. The deep learning model predicts radon in the coastal ocean using easily and inexpensively measurable parameters. Long-term radon time series are frequently impractical at many sites; thus, once trained and tested, this method allows for increasing generation of spatial and temporal radon artificial data in new understudied regions such as the Arctic, South America, and Africa where SGD tracer observations are lacking.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Sites and Data Acquisition

Radon data were acquired from globally diverse hydrogeological settings from researchers in the SGD community (Figure 2 and Table 1). Criteria for inclusion in this study were radon time series collected from coastal surface waters of at least 1-hr resolution. Sites were selected based on the availability of dissolved radon time series in coastal waters coupled with salinity, water temperature, and water column depth data. For each study site, radon measurements were collected from a single depth in shallow nearshore waters that were not stratified. Accompanying meteorological (air temperature, wind speed 10 m above mean sea level) data were acquired from publicly available databases for each site.

2.2. Model Construction

Two deep learning models were constructed to predict radon concentrations in coastal seawater as a proxy for SGD. The models were built in Python 3.6 using TensorFlow 2.6 (Abadi et al., 2015) with Keras Application

Table 1
Site Parameters for Data Used in This Study

Type	Study site	Latitude, longitude	Dates	n	Water depth (m)	Salinity	Water temperature (°C)	Air temperature (°C)	Wind speed (m/s)	²²² Rn (Bq/m ³)	References
Rocky	Kiholo Bay, HI, USA	19.86, -155.92	14 March 2014 to 6 July 2016	17,939	0.067 ± 0.21	17 ± 4.8	25 ± 1.6	21 ± 1.6	2.1 ± 0.42	370 ± 260	Dulai et al. (2016), McKenzie et al. (2021), RAW5 Puu Waawaa
	Black Point, HI, USA	21.26, -157.79	11 August to 9 September 2015	682	1.1 ± 0.16	32 ± 2.3	29 ± 1.1	28 ± 1.5	3.2 ± 2.2	1,300 ± 950	Richardson et al. (2017)
	Waiupe, HI, USA	21.28, -156.76	9 September to 7 October 2015	658	0.66 ± 0.18	30 ± 3.3	27 ± 1.6	27 ± 1.5	4.5 ± 2.2	300 ± 260	Richardson et al. (2017)
	Kasistna Bay, AK, USA	59.47, -151.55	19–22 July 2012	179	8.8 ± 5.7	28 ± 1.7	11 ± 0.54	12 ± 2.0	1.1 ± 1.0	27 ± 8.8	Dimova et al. (2015)
	Gakko River, Japan	39.05, 139.89	21–23 July 2009	44	0.95 ± 0.12	2.2 ± 3.1	19 ± 1.6	21 ± 3.9	2.8 ± 1.8	400 ± 130	Hosono et al. (2012)
	Honokohau Harbor, HI, USA	19.67, -156.03	14–16 February 2006	34	8.1 ± 0.67	24 ± 1.2	22 ± 2.5	22 ± 1.3	0.36 ± 0.74	170 ± 28	Peterson et al. (2009)
	Kamaiso Bay, Japan	39.08, 139.87	21–23 July 2009	28	0.69 ± 0.12	25 ± 2.4	21 ± 0.92	21 ± 4.1	1.6 ± 0.59	3,600 ± 1,300	Hosono et al. (2012)
	Faga'alu Bay, American Samoa	14.27, 170.13	29–30 July 2015	9	1.1 ± 0.42	24 ± 3.5	25 ± 0.31	26 ± 0.25	5.7 ± 0.78	840 ± 380	Shuler et al. (2020)
Sandy	FSUCLM, FL, USA	29.92, -84.51	18 November 2005 to 15 October 2007	14,851	1.8 ± 0.32	32 ± 2.4	22 ± 6.5	19 ± 8.3	3.8 ± 2.6	87 ± 32	Santos et al. (2009), FAWN Carrabelle
	Dauphin Island, AL, USA	30.35, -88.08	19 May to 28 June 2014	1,888	2.1 ± 0.15	12 ± 3.4	28 ± 2.0	26 ± 1.9	3.3 ± 1.8	24 ± 10	Adyasari et al. (2021)
	Dor Beach, Israel	32.58, 34.91	23–29 March; 25–30 May 2006	347	0.83 ± 0.19	28 ± 8.8	21 ± 4.4	25 ± 3.4	4.4 ± 2.2	46 ± 42	Swarzenski et al. (2006) and Weinstein et al. (2007)
	One Tree Island, Australia	-23.51, 152.09	14–27 November 2017	296	0.64 ± 0.42	36 ± 0.079	25 ± 1.5	23 ± 3.2	4.1 ± 0.94	11 ± 3.9	Archibald et al. (2019)
	Hat Head, Australia	-31.05, 153.05	25–27 March; 7–10 June 2013	235	0.72 ± 0.34	12 ± 10	22 ± 1.2	19 ± 2.8	2.13 ± 1.75	130 ± 65	Sadat-Noori et al. (2015)
	Heron Island, Australia	-23.44, 151.91	8–17 October 2011	189	0.86 ± 0.57	37 ± 0.13	23 ± 1.3	25 ± 4.5	3.6 ± 2.3	14 ± 4.3	O'Reilly et al. (2015)
	Bali, Indonesia	-8.35, 115.21	3–9 December 2018	132	1.3 ± 0.45	34 ± 0.99	29 ± 0.70	28 ± 1.6	3.1 ± 1.7	19 ± 13	Santos (unpublished data)
	Hood Canal, WA, USA	47.65, -122.89	6–11 June 2006	111	4.2 ± 1.1	40 ± 2.5	15 ± 0.93	14 ± 1.4	3.9 ± 1.9	83 ± 57	Swarzenski et al. (2007)
	Rarotonga, Cook Islands	-28.20, 153.58	15–19 March 2012	79	0.70 ± 0.13	36 ± 0.52	27 ± 1.9	23 ± 2.0	3.2 ± 1.5	200 ± 70	Cyronak et al. (2014)

Table 1
Continued

Type	Study site	Latitude, longitude	Dates	<i>n</i>	Water depth (m)	Salinity	Water temperature (°C)	Air temperature (°C)	Wind speed (m/s)	²²² Rn (Bq/m ³)	References
	Sydney, Australia	-33.85, 151.22	19–22 November 2015	77	0.87 ± 0.37	37 ± 0.50	21 ± 0.37	24 ± 6.6	6.5 ± 2.8	12 ± 1.6	Sadat-Noori et al. (2015)
	Marina Lagoon, Egypt	30.82, 29.05	12–15 March 2009; 16–18 July 2010	70	1.8 ± 0.49	36 ± 3.5	22 ± 7.8	19 ± 5.7	4.6 ± 4.3	270 ± 170	El-Gamal et al. (2012)
	Manila Bay, Philippines	14.57, 120.95	28–30 May 2006	35	1.4 ± 0.47	31 ± 0.96	30 ± 0.70	22 ± 2.3	1.5 ± 1.9	34 ± 15	Burnett et al. (2009)
	Alziv, Israel	33.05, 35.10	14–15 June 2005	24	0.12 ± 0.059	40 ± 2.3	25 ± 0.96	24 ± 0.57	4.5 ± 1.2	59 ± 33	Weinstein et al. (2007)
	Little Lagoon, AL, USA	30.25, -87.77	21–22 May 2012	12	0.56 ± 0.16	31 ± 0.67	27 ± 1.2	21 ± 0.57	0.44 ± 1.1	12 ± 5.5	Su et al. (2014)
Muddy	Jacobs Well, Australia	-27.75, 153.36	3–19 November 2013	342	0.93 ± 0.46	36 ± 3.8	24 ± 2.3	21 ± 2.9	1.6 ± 1.0	110 ± 88	Call et al. (2015)
	Barwon Creek, Australia	-38.15, 144.51	21–27 November 2014	120	2.5 ± 0.34	35 ± 1.2	18 ± 1.4	17 ± 4.8	4.8 ± 2.2	71 ± 44	Tait et al. (2016)
	Hinchinbrook Island, Australia	-18.32, 146.23	16–21 July 2014	107	4.9 ± 0.51	35 ± 0.96	21 ± 0.59	17 ± 5.0	4.5 ± 1.3	70 ± 9.3	Tait et al. (2016)
	Darwin, Australia	-12.45, 130.84	29 July to 3 August 2014	106	4.7 ± 1.7	27 ± 0.47	35 ± 2.0	26 ± 3.9	4.1 ± 2.3	57 ± 15	Tait et al. (2016)
	Tom's Creek, Australia	-23.80, 151.17	8 to 13 July 2014	69	1.4 ± 0.74	38 ± 1.2	17 ± 1.4	15 ± 6.3	3.3 ± 1.7	56 ± 37	Tait et al. (2016)

Note. Latitude, longitude, dates of sampling, number of samples used in the model after postprocessing, and aquifer type are indicated for each study site. Mean water depth (m), salinity, water temperature (°C), air temperature (°C), wind speed (m/s), and radon in water concentrations (Bq/m³) refer to the geometric mean of the data set ±2σ. Meteorological data were obtained from The Weather Company (2022) www.wunderground.com, unless otherwise indicated.

Programming Interface (API) and executed in Google Colaboratory. Radon concentrations were modeled using two different neural network frameworks—a 1D-CNN combined with RNN (1D-CNN-RNN) and a FCNN. The applied neural network algorithms were selected because they are well-suited for the data type (time series) and the objectives of the research. The 1D-CNN-RNN combines two frameworks frequently used for time series data, whereas the FCNN allows for radon to be considered as an independent output (i.e., compared to temporal frameworks, which use previous outputs to generate future results). The 1D-CNN-RNN framework is intended for gap filling, and short-term local-scale predictions (+1–24 hr), whereas the FCNN can be used for longer-term radon predictions using input data from a conductivity, temperature, and depth (CTD) sensor and commonly observed meteorological data (air temperature and wind speed). Input data were selected based on commonly observed parameters and model convergence. Feature scaling of data is a typical preprocessing step prior to deep learning. For training purposes, data were normalized between 0 and 1 for both models (Equation 1):

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (1)$$

Both models were trained with an 80/20 training and validation split (80% of data used for training with the remaining 20% reserved for model validation) and inputs were optimized in a stepwise manner that minimized the loss function, or the mean absolute error (MAE). We used an Adam optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2015) and fitted the models with a learning rate optimizer and early stopping to prevent overfitting of the data and to optimize model efficiency (Darken et al., 1992; Finnoff et al., 1993; Prechelt, 2012). Model performance metrics included minimization of the MAE and root mean square error (RMSE), in addition to comparing observed versus predicted data using the r^2 value as a quantitative measure of model success. The model code and input data are freely available (McKenzie et al., 2023a, 2023b).

2.2.1. 1D-CNN-RNN Model

The first model was constructed based on a 1D-CNN framework (Brownlee, 2018; LeCun et al., 1989) frequently used for time series due to its pattern recognition and signal processing abilities. Once the convolutional layers capture and process the important patterns/representations of the input time series data, Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) (Cho et al., 2014), one of the widely used models in RNNs, was applied to identify temporal dependency between the learned representations to better predict future parameters. The 1D-CNN-RNN framework used values of parameters for the previous “ n ” time steps to predict future “ m ” time steps. Preprocessing of data included calculating a 12-hr moving average and normalizing data (Equation 1). Model parameters included water depth, water temperature, salinity, and radon concentrations as both inputs and outputs. The 1D-CNN-RNN model was first trained with the Kiholo data set with an 80/20 train/validation split. Then we further validated the model from other study sites with sufficient data (exceeding 27 consecutive hours), regardless of the geological setting.

The 1D-CNN-RNN model itself consists of 10 hidden layers, including two 1D-Convolutional (1DConv) layers, followed by a max pooling layer (Zhou & Chellappa, 1988), two gated recurrent unit (GRU) layers, and then four fully connected layers (Figure S1 in Supporting Information S1). The maxpooling layer reduces the dimensionality by extracting the maximum values within a cluster from the previous convolutional layer. The 1DConv and GRU layers use a ReLU activation function (Equation 2), whereas the fully connected layers use an eLU activation function (Equation 3), where α is a predefined constant (more information can be found in the Keras documentation online):

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{ELU}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{for } x \geq 0 \\ \alpha(e^x - 1) & \text{for } x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

2.2.2. FCNN Model

The second model was constructed using a FCNN feed-forward framework using backpropagation (Keller et al., 2016). Inputs included coastal water depth, temperature, salinity, air temperature, and wind speed. These parameters were used to predict radon in water concentrations (activities in Bq/m³). The FCNN framework

accounts for each input variable independently and does not have integrated time dependence. Temporality was added in the model by including water depth, temperature, and salinity at ± 1 through 6 hr as inputs. Preprocessing of data included normalization (Equation 1) and shuffling (randomization). The FCNN model consists of 11 fully connected hidden layers (Figure S1 in Supporting Information S1) and uses ReLU, SELU, tanh, and linear activation functions (Equations 2 and 4–6), where α and λ are predefined constants.

$$\text{SELU}(x) = \lambda \begin{cases} x & \text{for } x > 0 \\ \alpha(e^x - 1) & \text{for } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\tanh(x) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2x}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Linear}(x) = ax + b \quad (6)$$

2.3. Model Validation

In addition to monitoring the MAE, RMSE, and r^2 values, equivalence testing was conducted for the FCNN model to assess model accuracy. Equivalence between observed and modeled radon was tested using the two-sided t test (TOST) in the statsmodels Python package (Schuirmann, 1987; Seabold & Perktold., 2010). Briefly, the TOST tests for similarity between two data sets with the null hypothesis (H_0 ; Equation 7) that the difference in the means of the observed (\bar{y}) and predicted (\bar{y}_{pred}) data is less than the lower threshold (low) or greater than the upper threshold (up) values. The alternate hypothesis (H_1 ; Equation 8) is that the difference between the predicted and observed data is within the equivalence threshold. The equivalence threshold was determined using the Cohen's D effect size. The null hypothesis is rejected if the TOST test p value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicating that the means of the two data sets are equivalent (Schuirmann, 1987):

$$H_0 = \bar{y} - \bar{y}_{pred} < low \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{y} - \bar{y}_{pred} > up \quad (7)$$

$$H_1 = low < \bar{y} - \bar{y}_{pred} < up \quad (8)$$

3. Results

The data used for model training and validation represented a wide range of study site characteristics and environmental parameters. For input parameters used in both the 1D-CNN-RNN and FCNN models, water depth (with respect to mean sea level) ranged from -1.7 to 17 m (mean = 0.99 ± 1.2 m), salinity ranged from 0.12 to 49 (mean = 24 ± 8.6), and water temperature ranged from 9.0 to 37°C (mean = $24 \pm 4.8^\circ\text{C}$). For the additional input parameters used in the FCNN model, wind speed ranged from 0 to 20 m/s (mean = 3.0 ± 2.0 m/s) and air temperature ranged from -6.8 to 42°C (mean = $21 \pm 5.8^\circ\text{C}$). Model output (radon) for both models ranged from 0 to $7,200$ Bq/m³ (mean = 240 ± 310 Bq/m³).

3.1. 1D-CNN-RNN Model Results

The 1D-CNN-RNN model, which is intended for local-scale, short-term (up to +24 hr) prediction, accurately predicted short-term future radon concentrations using salinity, water depth, water temperature, and radon from previous time steps. The MAE after 298 epochs (number of times the machine learning algorithm passes through the training set) assuming using the previous 6 hr to predict 1 hr in the future was 0.015 for both the training and validation sets (Figure 3 and Figure S2 in Supporting Information S1). The trained 1D-CNN-RNN model was then applied to 21 additional locations that had a length exceeding 27 hr (minimum requirement for model to run, which is limited by the length of the smoothing window and number of input steps) after applying the 12-hr moving average. The r^2 between predicted and observed radon ranged from 0.80 to 0.99 and the MAE from 0.18 to 0.43 (Table S1 in Supporting Information S1). Increased range of water temperatures was associated with greater model success (Figure S3 in Supporting Information S1). For locations with at least 2 weeks of hourly data (capturing the spring-neap tidal cycle), the r^2 between predicted and observed radon ranged from 0.96 to 0.99 and the MAE ranged from 0.18 to 0.24 (Figure 3). The 1D-CNN-RNN length of forecast can be modified.

A. 1D-CNN: Observed vs. predicted radon

B. 1D-CNN: Observed & predicted radon vs. time

Figure 3. Examples of one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN-RNN) predicted radon results from each aquifer type using the previous six time steps to predict one future time step. (a) Observed normalized radon data versus 1D-CNN-RNN predicted radon. Plots show Kīholo Bay training (purple dots) and validation (purple x's) sets (rocky aquifer example). Example results from a sandy (FSUCML) and muddy (Jacobs Well) sites are also shown. Resulting r^2 values between observed and predicted radon for the Kīholo Bay training ($r^2 = 0.97$) and validation ($r^2 = 0.92$) sets, and other locations (r^2 ranging from 0.96 to 0.99). (b) Observed normalized radon data (solid line) versus 1D-CNN-RNN predicted (dashed line) radon with respect to time (hours) for the three example sites in (a). The train/validation split for the Kīholo data set is indicated by a dotted line.

However, model success declines with increasing hours predicted in the future as expected (Figure 4). In this case, larger data sets clearly produce better predictions.

3.2. FCNN Model Results

The FCNN model, unlike the 1D-CNN-RNN model, does not use radon as an input variable, meaning it predicts radon using only parameters that are often readily available. The FCNN-predicted radon concentrations with

Figure 4. Example scenarios of one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN-RNN) model results for radon by varying the number of input and output time steps (each time step represents n and m hour intervals) for each aquifer type. For example, the first column $(-6, +1)$ refers to the example scenario using previous 6 hr to predict 1 hr in the future. The resulting r^2 corresponding to the color bar (ranging from 0.75 to 0.99) is given for each example location and scenario.

results, it is better suited for shorter term predictions (1–24 hr; Figure 4). For instance, the model can fill gaps related to loss of data from intermittent sensor malfunction. The 1D-CNN-RNN model can also be used for short-term future prediction, however, its ability for accurate prediction is driven by the consistency and length of the data set (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Observed normalized radon data versus fully connected neural network (FCNN)-predicted radon data for both training (dots) and validation (x's) sets. Resulting r^2 values between observed and predicted Rn demonstrate that the FCNN model adequately predicts both the training ($r^2 = 0.87$) and validation ($r^2 = 0.76$) sets. Excluding the highest radon concentrations (normalized radon >0.5 or $2,500 \text{ Bq/m}^3$), r^2 values are 0.85 and 0.73 for the training and validation sets, respectively. Colors represent aquifer type (purple = rocky, $n = 19,720$); light green = sandy, $n = 18,681$; light blue = muddy, $n = 837$). The root mean square error (RMSE) was 0.016 and 0.022 for training and validation sets, respectively.

high accuracy using salinity, water temperature, water depth, air temperature, and wind speed as input parameters (Figure 5). After 205 epochs, model loss during the training and validation periods were 0.0084 and 0.012, respectively (Figure S2 in Supporting Information S1). Model-predicted radon significantly agreed with observed radon for training ($r^2 = 0.87$) and validation ($r^2 = 0.76$) sets (Figure 5).

Statistical equivalence testing between predicted and observed radon using the TOST indicated that the observed and predicted radon means were statistically equivalent (p value < 0.0001). The difference in normalized radon concentration means ($\bar{y} - \bar{y}_{pred}$) for the training set was 3.8×10^{-4} and 1.3×10^{-4} for the validation set, further illustrating the success of this method in predicting radon. Similarly, we checked that the training and validation sets were representative of the same data ($y_{train} - y_{valid} = 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$).

4. Discussion

4.1. Missing Data Interpolation and Short-Term Future Prediction

The 1D-CNN-RNN model relies on temporal relationships and thus has radon (as well as salinity, water temperature, and depth) as both input and output parameters. While the 1D-CNN-RNN model boasts highly accurate results, it is better suited for shorter term predictions (1–24 hr; Figure 4). For instance, the model can fill gaps related to loss of data from intermittent sensor malfunction. The 1D-CNN-RNN model can also be used for short-term future prediction, however, its ability for accurate prediction is driven by the consistency and length of the data set (Figure 4).

The 1D-CNN-RNN model applies a technique where the model is trained and validated on one data set, and the relationships that the model learns from that data set are then applied to other data sets. The 2-year long Kiholo Bay data set represents SGD from a volcanic aquifer setting, and captures a variety of scenarios, including tropical storms, major precipitation events, and sea level anomalies (McKenzie et al., 2021). Given that 1D-CNN-RNN successfully modeled a range of aquifer types and SGD settings, the model can effectively uncover the underlying temporal relationships driving radon and perhaps coastal groundwater discharge.

To further confirm the capability of the model to recognize these underlying relationships, we also tested a scenario where the model was trained and validated using the FSUCML data set (the second longest data set used in this study). The FSUCML-trained model produced similar results (r^2 between predicted and observed radon for the FSUCML-trained model ranged from 0.66 to 0.97 compared to the Kiholo-trained model, which ranged from 0.80 to 0.99; Figure 6). We attribute the slight differences in model success between the Kiholo and FSUCML-trained models to the reduced length of the FSUCML record. While we only present results for data sets with more than 2 weeks in duration, the 1D-CNN-RNN model can be used for short-term (e.g., 1 hr) gap filling on significantly shorter data sets (Figure S4 in Supporting Information S1).

4.2. Simplified Prediction of Coastal Seawater Radon Activities

The FCNN model enables long-term radon prediction using only easy-to-obtain CTD and local metrological data ($r^2 = 0.76$) from short-term monitoring of radon. This technique simplifies data collection and reduces financial, personnel, and equipment costs.

Figure 6. Comparison between observed versus predicted coastal radon r^2 for the Kiholo (light blue) and FSUCML (dark blue) trained one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN-RNN) models. The two models performed similarly, while the Kiholo-trained model resulted in statistically comparable or higher r^2 values for all test sites except Heron Island and Honokohau.

Average uncertainty associated with radon in water measurements ranges from 5 to >50% (e.g., Dulai et al., 2016) depending on the method used (e.g., radon-in-air detectors, liquid scintillation, or gamma spectrometry), the concentrations encountered, and duration of measurements. The FCNN model resulted in an average uncertainty (defined by the MAE) of about 2.5% between observed and predicted radon results, well within an acceptable range of uncertainty. Interestingly, the FCNN model did not converge without the inclusion of air temperature and wind speed as inputs. Both air temperature and wind speed significantly influence atmospheric evasion of radon especially in shallow coastal environments (Burnett et al., 2007), further demonstrating the importance of accounting for radon loss to the atmosphere when assessing a coastal radon mass balance.

Despite SGD being a well-established vector for pollutants to reach the coastal ocean, field-based SGD estimates are absent for some of the most vulnerable areas to pollution and adverse effects from climate change such as the Indian sub-continent, South America, and the Indo-Pacific Coral Triangle (Pörtner et al., 2022). The methods presented here, particularly the FCNN model, can serve as a first approximation of temporal trends of radon in these regions following a short field collection period. Approaches and uncertainties associated with radon time series measurements (e.g., Adyasari et al., 2023; Burnett et al., 2007), such as the spatial extent of a radon plume need to be considered to apply the deep learning models or estimate SGD. The radon observations and deep learning results represent only the location of each time series deployment. In the few locations where multiple radon time series were deployed concurrently, the radon signal was homogenous within ~300 m off the nearshore source (Sadat-Noori et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2009). We outline the best practice to generate radon data for a new study site using the FCNN (see Text S1 for advice on how to retrain and use the model).

Deep learning models rely on the patterns and dependency learned from the training data, and thus predictive success is limited by both the size of the data set and homogeneity of those underlying relationships (Sarker, 2021). As the data set increases in size, deep learning algorithms can increasingly account for greater ranges in variability and learn new internal representations associated with the spatiotemporal dependency in real-world applications. For instance, this is demonstrated with the slight differences in results for the Kiholo versus FSUCML-trained 1D-CNN-RNN model. Here, we demonstrate how deep learning predicts radon concentrations with a relatively small data set. As many deep learning models are trained on millions of datapoints, there are opportunities for model improvement as more data become available (Sarker, 2021).

One limitation of this model is derived from the size of the data set and variability of natural conditions. A wide range of study settings were used in our model. For instance, data used in the FCNN model training and validation disproportionately represent rocky (51%) and sandy (47%) aquifers, with only 2% representing muddy shorelines. The skew in SGD studies toward nonmuddy aquifers is well documented (e.g., Taniguchi et al., 2019). Only five out of the 27 time series used here were obtained in muddy environments. Muddy mangroves and saltmarshes are hotspots of tidally driven groundwater flows (Chen et al., 2018) and cover long sections of tropical and

subtropical coastlines. Collection of more data in muddy environments is clearly a priority for future studies (Taniguchi et al., 2019). Future iterations of this model will expand aquifer type representation. Another limitation in the FCNN model is that 85% of radon activities used in the model are under 500 Bq/m³. While this range is representative of previous coastal studies (e.g., Adyasari et al., 2023; Taniguchi et al., 2019), model results may have lower accuracy for new locations with high radon concentrations (>500 Bq/m³) because the model learned from a limited number of data points. Additionally, the data used to train the model may be biased toward areas with likely SGD is implicated, reflecting a predisposition toward conducting temporal radon field studies where SGD is occurring. For this reason, it is important to first retrain the model for a new study site with field data.

This research represents a step toward the future and maturation of SGD research addressing long-standing issues with upscaling and spatiotemporal coverage of SGD data. Recent efforts for estimating global SGD and associated chemical loads have been made; for instance, through hydrological, numerical, and inverse modeling (e.g., Cho et al., 2018; Kwon et al., 2014; Luijendijk et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2019). The deep learning models presented here have two major advantages. First, both deep learning models have relatively simple data inputs. For instance, hydrological models typically rely on well-characterized hydrogeological and study site characteristics (e.g., Taniguchi et al., 2019), which are not necessary inputs for the deep learning model. Second, the deep learning models generate high temporal resolution coastal radon predictions following a short radon data collection period. However, the radon-deep learning models do not directly predict SGD. A full radon mass balance (e.g., Adyasari et al., 2023; Burnett & Dulaiova, 2003; Dulaiova et al., 2010) is still required to derive SGD estimates. For direct SGD prediction, we would require additional site-specific information, such as coastal morphology, groundwater radon concentrations, and SGD plume area and thickness (e.g., Adyasari et al., 2023; Burnett et al., 2007; Rodellas et al., 2021) because coastal seawater radon activities do not directly translate to SGD rates. The additional information required to estimate SGD is not available for most sites, so it is not possible to go as far as predicting SGD. Future development of deep learning models may help reduce uncertainty and improve global estimates.

We invite coastal hydrologists using radon as a groundwater tracer to contribute data to the shared data sets in this study. Our models can make temporal radon predictions at sites with limited data to extend time series but are not capable of performing spatial extrapolations, that is, predict radon where training data do not exist. To achieve global scale spatial extrapolations, 1-hr resolution radon, CTD, and meteorological training data on a global scale would be required. We see the approach presented here as a beginning step for the SGD community to create longer data sets including larger ranges in hydrologic conditions especially considering increasing trends in sea level and coastal flooding, decreasing trends in aquifer groundwater storage, and the need of better spatial coverage of the global coastlines. The SGD community should aim to collect data sets with at least the minimum number of parameters presented here to truly globalize the applicability of radon and data-driven approaches such as machine learning and deep learning. Contextualizing SGD at the regional, continental, and global scales remains a challenge (e.g., Luijendijk et al., 2020; Moosdorf et al., 2021; Taniguchi et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2019), meaning our proposed machine learning efforts may aid in resolving these problems.

5. Conclusions

This is the first study applying deep learning to radon and SGD research. Our results demonstrate the utility of artificial intelligence approaches to field-based hydrological and SGD research and support our hypothesis that deep learning is a viable method for predicting coastal radon concentrations. The 1D-CNN-RNN mode offers site-specific simulations of radon concentrations with high accuracy ($r^2_{\text{test}} = 0.80$ to 0.99). This model can be used for gap filling or short-term (+1–24 hr) future prediction. The FCNN model can discern commonalities and extract patterns dictating coastal seawater radon regardless of study site characteristics, aquifer type, and tidal stage. This model accurately predicts radon concentrations ($r^2_{\text{training}} = 0.87$, $r^2_{\text{validation}} = 0.76$) using only easily obtainable seawater and meteorological data as inputs.

Our baseline models using deep learning opens an exciting avenue for future SGD research. SGD field studies are only representative of the conditions occurring during measurements. Past field studies have predominantly occurred in specific geographic regions and have omitted large areas of the globe, notably the Global South. Tools allowing for greater geographic coverage of SGD as well as spatiotemporal upscaling of SGD are needed to resolve land-sea interactions in the advent of a changing climate, sea level rise, and coastal aquifer salinization.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this study.

Data Availability Statement

Raw data are publicly available are published on Zenodo (McKenzie et al., 2023b). Model code (Radon-Deep-Learning-1.0 v1.0.0) and preformatted input data are available on GitHub (<https://github.com/tamck/Radon-Deep-Learning-1.0>) and can also be accessed via Zenodo (McKenzie et al., 2023a).

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